

EraBoru, Afar, Ethiopia, a promising major geothermal site, with in a first step the demonstration of the Geothermal Village concept using a shallow steam resource

Jacques Varet, Ismael Ali Gardo, Peter Omenda,
AGAP (Ethiopia), SEPCO (Kenya) Géo2D (France)
jacques.varet@gmail.com ; gardoali2019@gmail.com ; pomenda@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

EraBoru is located in central-western Afar, in Ethiopia. This exceptional geothermal site benefits from a particularly favorable geodynamic context, in a transform fault zone between the two active spreading segments of Alayta and Manda Harraro (Varet et al. 2020). A plateau 700m high affected by normal faults and open fissures through which numerous silicic peralkaline obsidian domes and pumice cones were emplaced in the last 10 to 100ky. The last being the Dabbahu pyroclastic Event (Sept. 2005) opening a sequence of basaltic diking over a length of up to 70km and a width reaching 8 cm in the period 2005-2010 (Wright et al. 2006; Hamling et al. 2009, 2010)

Over a length exceeding 5 km and a width of 2-3 km, EraBoru (meaning steaming basin in Afar language) is affected by innumerable steam vents, occurring through normal faults and open fissures as well as diffuse vents at the surface of lava flows, domes and pyroclastic deposits. These hydrothermal manifestations are called “Boina” in Afar language, a name also used to describe the site (Barberi et al. 1972). And the geothermal grass (called “Fiale”) is also abundant along faults and lava flow surfaces. The characteristic of EraBoru – and of other sites around Dabbahu Volcano which provides an exceptional heat source (Johnson et al., 2016) – is the fact that the local population developed artisanal engineering solutions allowing to condense the steam and produce potable water for people and herds. An option of real resilience, as the water is produced continuously, whatever the climate fluctuation. Gardo & Varet (2020) could speak of a “geothermal civilisation” as human settlements are directly relying upon this resource used locally.

With Jérôme Ammann, CNRS research engineer at the University of Western Brittany, an infrared drone survey was undertaken, allowing a precise, quantitative mapping of the steam vents, whether natural or engineered. Coupled with field observations, it appears that, after having located the condensation wells on steam emergences, along upper compartments of active normal faults, more efficient solutions were developed drilling in the graben filled with pyroclastic layers of silicic ash and pumice falls where no surface manifestation is observed at the surface, but under a few metres (5 and up to 20), after digging through these dry (and cold) volcanogenic sediments, a wet surface is met, in which the steam produced a hydrothermally altered clay zone. Drilling through this layer allows to produce steam under pressure, with much better flow rates than the superficial captures of naturally emerging steam. While a shallow geophysical survey will be engaged allowing to determine optimal targets, in terms of depth, geological formations and reservoir extension, while in the meantime, the necessary drilling and well-head equipment training programme will be provided by SEPCO to AGAP, allowing to use the water drilling equipment owned by the sister organization APDA, to undertake exploration drilling of hot wells up to 350 metres deep. The paper describes the site, the geothermal conceptual model, and the project of demonstration of the Geothermal Village at EraBoru.

I. INTRODUCTION

Era Boru, meaning “steaming crater” is a geothermal site located in central-western Afar, with a population of over thousand settled in the area, 20 Km² wide, benefits from these important steam manifestations. A geothermal exploration and feasibility study was engaged by the LEAP-RE EU-AU interdisciplinary team, including the anthropological study of this “geothermal civilisation” (Gardo & Varet, 2020). The demonstration site of the “Geothermal Village” concept, hopefully resulting from research project should open perspective for energy and water production on off-grid sites in the whole region.

1.1. Regional context of Afar geothermal sites

Afar is one of the hottest and driest places in the world. Although it is severely affected by climate change, it is an area where a population has been living since immemorial times, adapting its pastoralist activities to changing environmental conditions. The Afar triangle; name derived from the one of the local inhabitants, extends over 3 countries (NE Ethiopia, SE Eritrea, and W Djibouti Republic); the main surface and the majority of the population (over one million) being found in Ethiopia. Since the Federal Democratic Republic was promulgated, Afar benefits from the status of a “Regional State” in Ethiopia, with Semara as its capital.

Afar displays a particular geodynamic situation, as it is not just the northern extension of the East African Rift System (EARS), but in fact part of the Red Sea – Gulf of Aden oceanic rift system, exceptionally emerged there, on the African continent. Afar does not represent the “funneling out” of the MER but a specific area where the continental MER hits the out-cropping Aden-Red Sea oceanic ridge, represented by “axial volcanic ranges” where the active spreading concentrate (Tazieff et al., 1970, Barberi et al., 1972). The Afar floor (-120m bsl to the north and – 155m bsl to the east) is surrounded by the escarpments of the Nubian plate to the West, the Somalian plate to the South and the Arabic plate to the East, with the Arrata block (earlier called Danakil Alps) acting as a microplate rotating anticlockwise in-between the Southern Red Sea and the former Danakil sea, whereas the SE part acts as an accretion of the Arabia plate (Varet, 20018 ; Fig.1).

The floor of the Afar triangle is covered by dominantly basaltic lava piles, called the Afar Stratoid series, ranging in age from 4 to 1 My (Barberi et al., 1972). This unit is extensively faulted (active normal faults and open fissures). From North (Gulf of Zula in Eritrea) to South-East (Gulf of Tadjourah in Djibouti), several well-defined spreading segments expressed at the surface by basaltic axial ranges developed in the last 1 My and are all active (Fig.2). All are oriented in a NNW-SSE (in the NW part) to NW-SE direction (in the Eastern part), coherent with the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden Mid-Oceanic Ridges (MOR) segments. Along both sides, transverse ranges and central silicic volcanoes – equally recent and active – are observed in areas of discontinuities of the basement. They eventually mark transverse fracture zones (TFZ). These central volcanoes show similitude with those found in South-West Afar along the MER northern extension. Both active faulting of the stratoid series and these various active volcanic units provide numerous opportunities for the development of surface heat release, under various forms, dominantly as fumaroles, steam vents and hot-wet grounds.

As a result, with the exception of its stabilized margins, the whole Afar floor benefits - despite a generally deep-water table from this particular form of groundwater (steam!), thanks to convective systems emerging at the surface through open faults. All emissive sites are known – and named as such (“*boyna*”) – by the local pastoralist population, which will use them for water production by condensation and also as graze-lands thanks to specific vegetation (“*fiale*”) developed on these wet environments in which sand and dust brought by the wind will contribute to the development of soils, together with the red clays produced by hydrothermal alteration of the volcanic rocks. In many places these sites are used temporarily in the most arid periods, which tend to become more frequent due to climate change.

Fig.1: The Afar triangle and surrounding region (modified from Keir et al., 2012). The anticlockwise rotation Arrata Block is shown in pale color whereas the Arabia accretion is in yellow. The orange triangles show Holocene volcanoes. The grey circles show large (>ML 3) earthquakes. The black earthquake focal mechanisms are from the Global Centroid Moment Tensor catalogue, the red earthquake from Illsley-Kemp et al. (2018). Bottom right inset: Plate motions relative to a fixed Nubian plate (ArRajehi et al., 2010). The violet rectangle limits the studied EraBoru area in the TFZ between Alayta and Manda Harraro axial ranges and spreading segments.

Fig. 2: Geological sketch map of Afar (after CNR-CNRS, 1973; Varet, 1975; Beyene & Abdelsalam, 2005, modified) showing the location of Era Boru (yellow rectangle) and the volcanic units of Afar (from Miocene to present).

1.2. Local geodynamic context

As shown in Fig. 1 and 2, Dabbahu volcanic centre developed in the context of the axial volcanic ranges, identified by Barberi & Varet (1975) as the presently active segments within Afar. It in fact sits between the southern extremity of Alayta to the north and the northern extremity of Manda Harraro range to the south (Fig.6). It was then identified as a fast-spreading

segment, and the 2005-2010 event did prove it thanks to the numerous geophysical studies engaged by several international teams immediately after the first sismo-volcanic event which was then called Dabbahu. (Grandin et al., 2010; Ebinger et al., 2010; Field et al. 2012) But it happened in fact at the place now called EraBoru

Fig.3: Extract from the geological map of Afar (CNR-CNRS, 1971, 1975). The bottom of faulted escarpment discontinuities is underlined in dark brown. Spreading axis of axial ranges are underlined in red. Transverse volcano-tectonic structures are underlined in violet.

The plate tectonic interpretation shows Fracture Zone (FZ) and Transform Fault (TF). Era Boru is located at the TF Zone linking Alayta spreading segment N to Manda Harraro S. From Omenda & Varet (2020)

1.3. Geographic, hydrological & geological context of Era Boru geothermal site

Extensive field surveys in Afar show that the geothermal resource has extensively been used by the local population for a long time, at least few thousand years, since the climate changed from wet to dry (4,800 years BP). With the noticeable exception of southern Afar, where the Awash River basins never dries, and the marginal grabens fed by short rivers along the faulted Nubian escarpment, the use of geothermal resource appears as generalized (most fumaroles are equipped). These steaming sites are numerous along the volcanic ranges and centres, as well as along active faults and open fissures affecting the basalts and rhyolites of the stratoid series. Most appear to have been engineered by the local population in order to recover water by condensation of the steam. In some areas where seasonal pastures and water points are temporarily available these devices are only used by nomads as refuge in case of heavy drought. These devices are the only safe source of water, throughout the year, whatever the climate. These geothermal manifestations extend over several tens of square kilometres, in which hundreds of steam wells have been engineered and are still operating currently. This innovative solution developed while the area was rather isolated, separated from access roads by rough lava fields. But it is now accessible in 1:30 hour from the Teru plain (and nearest town), itself reached in 2:30 hour drive along a well-maintained earth road from Semara, capital of the Afar Regional State.

Fig.3: Geological map of Dabbahu volcanic centre (CNR-CNRS, Varet, 1975) characterized by peralkaline obsidians (yellow) topping a shield volcano made of transitional basalts (blue) and intermediate lava (mugearite, dark trachyte, violet). The site earlier called “boyna” on the original map is now called “EraBoru” (red rectangle).

Teru is a wide, flat-lying sedimentary plain located at the foot of the Nubian escarpment. Over a width of 15 to 20 Km and a length of 45 Km, this plain at an average altitude of 300 metres developed a rather large green-grass and acacia forested land as it forms an endoreic basin closed East by the Alayta and Dabbahu lava fields and North by the Ma'Alalta central stratovolcano, fed by numerous short temporary river beds benefitting from the high pluviosity of the Nubian plateau border (Fig.4).

Fig. 4: DEM model showing the limits of the hydrographic basin of Teru (black contour), feeding – underneath the recent lava fields and thanks to transverse faults - the Era Boru geothermal system (yellow rectangle) from the Nubian plateau escarpment. Observe the marginal grabens along the foot of the escarpment. (from Varet, 2012)

1.3. A powerful magmatic heat source and a fractured steam reservoir

Initially called Boyna, Dabbahu volcano was established – from petrological, mineralogical and geochemical studies (Barberi et al. 1974a,b ; Bizouard et al. 1980) - as a textbook example of a full fractional crystallisation series ranging from initial transitional basalts up to pantellerites under low oxygen fugacity's, i.e. in a magma chamber located at shallow depth. The youngest volcanic rocks are peralkaline rhyolitic obsidians (ionic $\text{Na}+\text{K} > \text{Al}$), further subdivided into comendites and pantellerites, with pantellerite thick flows toping the volcano, and overlying the comendite. Both are dominantly found as lava flows, but can take the form of explosive tephra with pumice and ash, particularly along the eastern foot of the volcano. That is in the Era Boru plateau, which is cut by normal faults of N-S direction into half-grabens, partly filled with these unconsolidated silicic pyroclastic layers. The initial start of the major volcano-sismic Manda Harraro event (2005-2010) on Sept. 26, 2005, was a small rhyolitic ash and pumice eruption which occurred ~7 km from Dabbahu summit forming the Da'Ure vent ($12^{\circ} 39'00.58'' \text{ N}$, $40^{\circ} 31'10.43'' \text{ E}$). This is the first documented historical eruption in this area (Fig.5), which happened as a result of the largest dyke opening event ever described. It was accompanied by a set of local tectonic events including development of normal faults, opening of fissures of N-S direction, and vertical motions, with sinking up to 5 m of graben floors as observed along fault scarps (Fig.6).

Fig.5 Left: Satellite image of the 2005 eruptive event at Da'Ure, EraBoru area (Dabbahu eastern foot), showing the open fissure which emitted cinder and pumice of peralkaline silicic composition. Right : aerial view of the fissure vent of the same eruption, taken in October 2005, showing the post-eruptive scene. Photo by Asfawossen Asrat.

Fig.6: N-S normal fault escarpment bordering the eastern side of EraBoru central graben. Observe that, along this 10m throw, the lower half was produced during the 2005 event; steam wells are observed along this steaming fault Photo J.Varet, January 2024.

Calculations from minerals-liquid equilibria by Field et al (2012) confirm an entrapment depth of 1 to 6 km, whereas earthquake locations and S-wave attenuation beneath Dabbahu indicates a central earthquake-free void between 2 and 6 km, interpreted as an area of magma storage. Abundant earthquakes above 2 km suggest a fractured roof – hosting the steam leaking reservoir - above the magma chamber. Ebinger et al. (2008) suggest the interpretation of a sill-like melt zone between 3 and 5 km depth. As a whole, data suggests a consistency in the magma storage beneath Dabbahu over the last few thousand years. This long-term stability not only contributed to the evolved nature of such abundant most recent eruptive products, but also favours the presence of a remanent magmatic heat source for this large geothermal system.

It appears that the Dabbahu-Manda Harraro event in fact initially developed – as far as this could be measured while the site was not really equipped before the 2005 eruption – in the EraBoru area selected for our geothermal project. As shown by Grandin et al. (2010), besides the Da’Ure eruption, the area located south from the Gab’ho obsidian dome appears to have undergone tectono-magmatic events, as illustrated by our own observations (Fig.6).

2. The Geothermal Village project site

2.1. The targetted area

The Era Boru geothermal site, as selected for the field reconnaissance engaged in January-February 2024, is bounded to the West by Dabbahu silicic peralkaline volcano, to the North and East by the basaltic lava fields emitted from Alayta axial range, and to the South by the basaltic fissural lava fields of Manda Harraro axial range (Fig.7). Within this space - a quadrangle of 8x15 km (dotted red on map Fig.7) -, the surface – made of silicic lava flows and pyroclasts (cinder and pumice layers) - is dissected by faults and open fissures of N-S to NNW-SSE directions, partly covered by later silicic centres emitted along the same volcano-tectonic trend forming a graben containing at least 3 rift-in rift structures. Note that, despite a few NW-SE trending faults and volcanic alignments, no clear transform fault is observed at the surface but a set of silicic peralkaline domes and flows, and a few pyroclastites cones (pumices and welded tuffs), emitted along feeding dikes of sub-N-S direction, as seen of Fig.8. This transform fault zone, 25 Km x 25 Km i.e. circa 600 Km² wide in fact acts as a set of short slow-spreading segments, favouring the development of crystal fractionation in shallow magma chambers (Barberi et al., 1975; Field et al. 2010; Gardo & Varet, 2018) with emission of silicic domes and steam leakages. A geothermal play type – similar to the one observed at Olkaria - favourable to giant site development (Omenda & Varet, 2020).

The Era Boru area is far the most spectacular, as continuous steam fields are covering an area exceeding 5 Km long and up to 3 km wide. Given (i) the exceptional importance of this steaming area, (ii) the importance of the population relying upon this resource, and now (iii)

these improved conditions of access, Era Boru was selected as the most suitable priority target for the GV project.

Fig.7 (Left): Satellite image of the wide Era Boru area, in the accommodation zone (transform fault zone), between the two spreading segments of Alayta to the north and Manda Harraro to the south. The whole area (rectangle dotted red, 8x15 km wide) is characterized by normal and open faults, silicic peralkaline lava-domes and pyroclasts craters. Within this large area, a more restricted quadrangle (yellow rectangle of 5x3km) was selected, detailed in Fig.8 (Right).

New field work (Jan-Feb. 2024) show an area dissected by normal faults of N-S to NNW-SSE direction, along which silicic lava domes and pyroclastic craters (10ky to present) where also emitted. The floor of this horst and graben is made of lava flow of intermediate composition emitted from the Dabbahu shield volcano, covered and filled in the garbens by pumice and cinder deposits. Open fissures are also observed, channelling the innumerable steam surface manifestations, despite being quickly obliterated by the light wind blown cinder (Fig.9).

Fig.9: E-W volcano-structural section through Era Boru geothermal site, located in an active rift with the two recent rift-in-rift silicic volcanic systems on both sides of the geothermal area. On the western side Gab'ho obsidian dome north with aligned pyroclastic units south, and on the eastern side, a large composite pyroclastites axial volcanic system to the north and silicic domes to the south. The surface manifestations (steam vents) develop along the numerous open and normal faults affecting the faulted floor o a 3 Km wide area, 700m above sea level.

2.2. The Afar artisanal steam well design

A population of 150 families (i.e. circa 1.000 habitants) live at EraBoru, relying upon geothermal steam answering their water needs. The solution of reference for the population is to condensate the natural steam vents for liquid water production and other uses (washing, boiling food and tea...). The technique is to improve the steaming of the fissures, faults and soils by digging, 1 up to 20 m deep, with a short hoe to enlarge the vent, removing the surface formations, stones, pumice and cinder, then reaching a clay layer produced by alteration of the volcanic products, and to install devices for channelling and condensing the steam. This is done building a dry-stone wall, 2 to 5 metres wide, allowing to fix horizontally acacias branches or other vegetation in order to collect the liquid water by condensation. The drops then fall in a basin made of the red clay (resulting from the hydrothermal alteration of the volcanic rocks) earlier extracted from the well. The water is then drawn out with a bucket and a rope (Fig.10). Depending on the topography, the basin may be directly accessible (in case of steep slope and fault scarp) or will be accessed with a bucket and a rope when located on a flat ground. Water is used for all kinds of human consumption, but mainly for herds of livestock in this pastoralist society.

Fig.10 (Left): Traditional device for water condensation from fumaroles (“Boina”) using acacia branches on a well dug along an emitting fault South of Dabbahu (Photo: J.Varet, 2016). Fig.5 (Left): Schematic cross section through a traditional geothermal steam condensing device as observed at Era Boru (from Gardo & Varet, 2020). Steam leaking from faults is channelled through a circular (2 to 5 m diameter) dry-stone wall and condensate through acacias branches. Liquid water is collected in a clay basin accessible through removeable opening in the dry-stone wall.

2.3. The numerous fairly recent silicic domes of the Era Boru area

Let’s examine successively some of the most representative silicic centres, all of very recent age (a few k years only), present in the area. Fig.9 is an E-W geological cross section through the area. It shows two major emissive silicic centres on both sides of a 7 km wide graben. Gab’ho - the largest (2,5 x 3 km) and most spectacular obsidian dome in the area - was emitted from a single eruptive point. Clearly built on a set of open fissures and normal faults of N-S direction, predating the eruption, it adjusted on the relief, filling the downfaulted blocks and half-grabens. But, as evidenced by satellite imagery (Fig.11) and confirmed by field observations, it was also affected by later faults and open fissures (generally replays of pre-existing faults), notably well visible North, South and East of the dome. The SE limit was particularly investigated as it corresponds to the northernmost extremity of the intensively steaming zone of Era Boru.

As illustrated in Fig.12, immediately south from Gab’ho, along the same tectonic alignment (faults underlined in red) a large silicic pyroclastic cone predating Gab’ho is observed, 3 Km long and 2 Km wide). It displays two volcanic features of interest: (i) an inflation event postdating the pumice eruption, formed by an uprising lava dome underneath the pyroclastic

cover, and (ii) along the axis of the volcano, the eruptive fissure gave birth to a set of elongated lava-domes, emitted from the same axial feeding dike, filling the gap between the two lips of the pyroclastic eruption. Interesting to note that the Da'Ure 2005 emissive fissure, of rather similar nature, but of the order of 10 times less important, is located on the SE side of this earlier eruption.

Fig.11: The Gab'ho obsidian dome, emitted on a faulted surface (underlined in red): general view (left) and detailed views of the northern eastern and southern parts, where sets of open fissures – replay of earlier faults - are shown to have affected the dome once consolidated, some of them resulting from the 2005 event.

Fig. 12: View of the pumice dome located immediately south from Gab'ho, sitting on the faulted lava surface. General view left, with details of its southern part right. While the northern half of this eruptive centre is characterized by a rather symmetrical crater, its southern half display a NNW-SSE. axial eruptive axis giving rise to an inflating dome and a final linear viscous lava eruption. At the SE foot of this volcano the Da'Ure 2005 eruptive event is underlined in yellow.

We limited the targeted area south where the viscous silicic flows emitted from Dabbahu (Fig.13), cover the rather flat-lying faulted plateau described above. We notice there a change in the structural pattern, with volcanic domes and cones that, although aligned N-S, appear to have been emitted under the control of earlier feeders of transverse (NE-SW) directions.

Fig.13: The area located south from Da'Ure is characterized by a set of composite silicic domes that, if aligned in the N-S direction? display structural patterns that indicate the incidence of transverse (NE-SW) direction for the feeding dikes and faults.

This area also marks the southern limit of the Era Boru steaming zone: whereas several domes and faults are affected by fumarolic activity, we prefer at this stage to close the prospect south, also due to access conditions.

As observed on Fig.14, immediately south from Da'Ure, two composite domes, displaying thick silicic flows at the base and topped by rather viscous domes and cones, are both controlled by NE-SW emissive axis. Further south, the relief is even more rugged, affected by thicker flows emitted from Dabbahu, with again younger complex domes emitted along feeding fissures displaying both N-S and NE-SW and even E-W directions (Fig.15). The area is so rugged that the fumarole zones are of rather difficult access and therefore not retained as targets at present stage for our geothermal project.

Fig. 14: Example of one of the complex silicic centre observed south from Era Boru area.

While partly emitted along faults of N-S direction, which also affected the edifice after consolidation, the emissive system appears as controlled by NE-SW and even eventually E-W feeders

. East from Gab'ho, as seen on Fig.8 and 9, an even larger and more complex silicic centre developed, along feeding faults of the same N-S direction, well visible in the successive steps of construction of the edifice (Fig. 17). First with thick flows, now visible on both East and West sides, then dissected by an axial graben, with a wide pyroclastic eruption, which ended with the emission of viscous flow along the same axis, which opened again with the formation of an axial graben. The obsidian flows (in yellow on Fig. 15) did extend N and S at both ends of the axial graben.

Fig.15: Complex silicic lava-dome and associated pyroclasts - 3,5 x 5 km wide - located east from Gabho, sitting on earlier faulted (underlined in red) lava flows. This polycyclic volcano is elongated in the N-S direction with an axial emissive zone having successively produced viscous dome-flows (observed on both sides), then a pyroclastic eruption (affected by erosion, on both sides) and finally viscous flows along the same emissive axis, the whole process resulting in the formation of two imbedded grabens. Note the presence of a small adventive obsidian dome emitted at the western foot of this eruptive centre along a transverse (NE-SW) direction.

Note that several other domes are located both South and North, a few Km away, on the same rift-in-rift axis, along this eastern side of Era Boru targeted area. One and half Km south from the silicic complex described in Fig. 15, a set of five domes, aligned N-S along the same feeding dike, emitted a 1.2 km wide viscous dome-flow. And on the SW side of it, another seven smaller domes are observed, with a clear influence of NE-SW trending faults developed along the southern flank of the main edifice. Here again with a proof of the influence of a transform fault zone (Fig.16) in the development of the EraBoru geothermal system.

Fig.16: South from the pyroclastic-lava-dome complex, a lava dome-flow is shown to be built on a N-S feeding dike, eventually the same as the one described in Fig.17. However, in this southern area, transverse faults (NE-SW) not only affect the foot of the dome, but also apparently determined the erection of a set of 7 smaller domes.

2.4. The floor of the EraBoru targeted zone

The floor of the targeted zone is characterized by a relatively flat-lying plateau, 700m high, surrounded by the silicic domes and pyroclastic emission centres described above. As observed in Fig.10, the area can be seen as a composite graben, 7 Km wide, divided in several rift-in-rifts 3 of them magmatically active and the central one - 3 km wide and purely tectonic but hydrothermally active - which was selected as geothermal target area. It is due to this configuration that the area is called “EraBoru”, meaning “*steaming crater, or basin*” in Afar language. The floor is made of lava flows of intermediate composition (mugearites) which were emitted from the Dabbahu volcano shield as deduced from the flow lines well visible at the surface of these flows.

If the area displays the same geological characteristics to the north and the south from Gab'ho dome, the area located to the south of the dome was chosen as the priority target for the project, as so many steam vents are observed in the whole area, along faults scarps and open fissures (Fig.17), and in the plains where steam wells are dugged by the Afar people to condensate the steam for water production (Fig.18 to 21).

Fig. 18; Typical view of EraBoru area, with steam vent along a fault zone and steam wells engineered by Afar people to condensate the steam for liquid water production.

Of 5x3 Km wide, the study engaged in the area should allow to define a more restricted target (of the order of 1 square Km) for the Geothermal Village project.

Fig. 19: All over the EraBoru area, steam – well visible early morning - is leaking all along faults and silicic domes

Fig. 20: in the central & S part of the area, the density of the steam wells reaches 1 per 100m²

The central part of the area is characterized by faults and open fissures, dissecting along N-S trends, the area in half-grabens, along which the steam natural vents are observed along the fault scarps, whereas in the plains filled by volcanic ash and pumice falls, the steam is emitted from wells engineered by the Afar people living on site.

Fig. 21: detailed satellite image showing the high density of steam wells in the EraBoru plateau, in areas covered by plat-lying pyroclastic deposits. Image Left is from the southern extremity of the area (east from Da'Ure), whereas on the right is shown part of the central zone at the NE foot of the large pumice cone described in Fig.12.

Fig.22- A: Up: satellite image of part of the central area of EraBoru. On both sides of the image, the grey colour corresponds to the lava flows (emitted from Dabbahu) forming the floor of the site, affected by normal faults (notably seen East) and open fissures as seen on the lava flow West.

Observe the numerous steam wells (circles averaging 5 m diameter)) dugged all across the graben floor, and particularly along its western half.

Fig.22 B: Down: photograph of the same area, with the steam wells in the plain between the two E & W fault escarpments (Photo J.Varet, Jan. 2024).

As seen in photos in Fig. 23, wells are dug manually, with successive steps, 2-3 m deep each, allowing workers to extract the pyroclastic layers until the clay zone covering the steam zone, is reached. Until this wet surface is reached, digging do not pose problems of heat, but once the clay zone is reached, working conditions become more problematic, and workers need to operate quickly in order to pierce down to the steam zone and engage production.

Fig. 23: steam well under construction. Two steps, 3 metres deep, are already dugged through the pumice and cinder cover . Digging will continue until the clay zone is reached. Then the well will be equipped with a vegetation cover allowing steam condensation and liquid water production.

The steam wells are then surrounded by a dry-stone wall allowing to fix branches of thick straw on which water will condensate. Drops of liquid water will fall in a clay basin from which the liquid will be extracted with a rope and a bucket manually and poured out in a clay basin allowing to feed the herds.

Fig. 24: Steam wells equipped for liquid water production by condensation (left) and distribution in a clay basin for answering humans and herds needs at Era Boru, (photo J.Varet, Jan. 2024).

3. The drone survey undertaken by Jérôme Hamman (CNRS, UBO, France)

3.1. Main thermal features captured

While determining the areas covered with the IR drone survey, we made sure that all kinds of geological environments controlling the thermal manifestations were captured by the flights selection: normal faults, open fissures, silicic domes apparently hydrothermally active. We also considered the sites engineered for steam capture and condensation.

The following results were obtained:

- a) *Normal fault (Fig.25)*
- b) *Open pyroclastic emissive fissures (Fig. 26)*
- c) *Silicic dome (Fig.27)*
- d) *Down-faulted surfaces filled with pyroclastic deposits (Fig.28)*
- e) *Engineered artisanal steam wells (Fig.29)*

Fig.25: IR picture of a hydrothermally active normal fault. The contrast is strong between the uplifted compartment, made of a lava flow, showing numerous steam leakages at the surface, with a high concentration of steam vents along the fault plane itself. The downfaulted side, filled with silicic pyroclastic formations (cinder and pumice) appear as cold, particularly all along the fault escarpment floor.

Fig.26: The Da'Ure 2005 event was characterized by a pyroclastic emission along an open fissure of N-direction, resulting in two lips and an elongated deep mouth. While the mouth itself appears as cold, hydrothermal activity is still present along the two lips (hydrothermal convection along the two walls).

Fig. 27: Silicic dome located in the southern part of EraBoru geothermal system. The dome is typically affected by hydrothermal activity (and alteration) in its summit part, with a N-S faults controlling the activity. Thermal manifestations are also developed along some flanks of the dome.

Fig. 28: The down-faulted compartments are filled with pyroclastic deposits (silicic cinder and pumice) generally unconsolidated. In this case, the open fissures affecting the area quickly disappear at the surface, filled with eolian sands (in fact silicic cinder).

However, in the southern part of the area, wide plains affected by historical hydrothermal activity developed surfaces that were weathered and consolidated by silica sinters over a few centimetres, so that the open fissuring could affect the surface, which then appears as favouring linear steam leakages revealed by the IR drone survey.

Fig. 29: As described above, the EraBoru area is characterized by the numerous steam wells which – through times – have been engineered by the local Afar population in order to recover liquid water from steam condensation. The pyroclastic surface deposits are removed until a clay zone is reached through which steam is condensated through a permeable vegetal roof ; the liquid water is then used for community's needs. As seen on the upper image, wells are either aligned – at a few meters distance - along the fault scarp (sometimes located right on the fault). But in the most suitable areas, steam wells are installed all over the surface of the plain, (as seen in the lower image)

3.2. An exceptional geothermal site, for local development with first the GV project and later industrial expansion

Era Boru area appears as a place, eventually unique in the world, where a complete social organization emerged, based on a direct relation of a human community with an exceptional geothermal resource with steam abundantly available at the surface of a wide plateau, isolated from the rest of the region given the difficult access conditions. For millennium, a sustained development demonstrated its efficiency. Now that a new road is being build, which will open this society to outside world, the opportunity arises for this geothermal resource to be used more efficiently for both energy and water production. With, as pictured in Fig. 30.

- I. an exceptionally large magmatic heat source,
- II. an abundant water recharge,
- III. various volcanic products (black lava, scoria, pyroclasts, pumice...) and active / complex fracturation determining high permeability for the geothermal reservoir
- IV. magmatic heat source, geothermal steam reservoir and clay cap confirmed by geophysics

Fig.30: Schematic E-W cross section through the median part of the site, perpendicular to the normal faults (plain red) and open fissure (double red lines) showing the various kinds of steam emissions at the surface. While steam is available at the surface and can be captured by shallow engineered steam wells along faults and open fissures (the most common type of Boina, as shown in section Fig.5), Afar local artisanal engineers realized that, digging deeper in the graben infilling & piercing through the clay layer acting as a cover allows to obtain better production at the surface (higher flow rate and temperatures)

CONCLUSION

Era Boru appears as a highly promising geothermal resource of major interest at national, regional and t start with, at local level. Given the importance of the civilisation that developed in the area thanks to the ancestral use of the geothermal steam, an in-depth socio-anthropological study was engaged under the LEAP EU-AU R&D Program, with active AGAP's involvement. This plateau, isolated for millenniums and separated from the surrounding Afar lowlands where communications by roads developed in the recent years, is now accessible with a new road under construction. This will induce changes in this society that need to be properly anticipated and accompanied. The Geothermal Village project will

obviously play a major role in a local development which is being appropriated by the people concerned. Unfortunately, the armed conflict between Tigray and the Federal State did not allow to provide the priority the project did merit. Conditions are now met to engage the necessary geophysical surveys. We hope that, despite these unforeseen circumstances, opportunities will be open to reach the feasibility stage of this Geothermal Village project on EraBoru site.

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